

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR AND DAMAGE PROGRESSION IN MULTILAYER WOVEN GLASS/VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Preforms containing orthogonal, normal layered interlock and offset layered interlock architectures were woven in E-glass and consolidated with vinyl ester resin. Tensile specimens were prepared, in the warp and weft directions, then tested to failure. The stress-strain response of most specimens were trilinear, with a primary softening of 20-30 % at 2500-3500 $\mu\epsilon$ and a secondary softening of 0-15 % at 10000-17000 $\mu\epsilon$. The difference in the elastic modulus and strength of all structures was within experimental scatter, provided the fibre content in the testing direction was accounted for. The strain to failure was similar for all specimens. Selected specimens were illuminated with transmitted light and photographed during testing. Cracks occurred within the tows oriented both perpendicular and parallel to the testing direction. Structures containing more heavily crimped warp tows also exhibited disbonding local to the warp tow/binder crossover point. The softening events were attributed to these cracks.

KEYWORDS: multilayer weave, modulus, tensile strength, strain to failure, softening, transmitted light photography, damage progression, crack distribution

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behaviour of textile composites can be predicted with reasonable reliability using a number of models [1-3]. The most critical variable in prediction is the orientation of tows relative to the loading axis. In all but the simplest approximations [3], these models must be experimentally calibrated with “real” structures, either by measuring the distribution of tow orientations in consolidated [1], or dry [4], preforms, or by calibrating models with experimental results from composites containing known fibre orientations [1].

Extensive pre-test and post-failure examinations have been used to develop these prediction models [1]. The mechanisms for load transfer and damage progression have had to satisfy both the stress-strain behaviour and the observed damage. While such work has proved extremely useful it does not precisely establish the progression of damage during loading. Interrupted testing, where specimens were unloaded prior to failure and then examined, provides definitive evidence of the progression of damage and has been used in the

development of predictive models, however it is a very laborious technique. A more convenient method would be to continuously monitor the specimen during testing. Damage accumulation would then be observed explicitly, and subsequent interrupted testing targeted to more closely examine critical events.

This paper describes the preliminary results for composites containing multilayer woven glass preforms in vinyl ester resin. Damage was monitored during testing by photographing specimens that had been illuminated with transmitted light, then post-failure by examining polished cross-sections. Detailed examination of the critical damage features reported in this work, using interrupted testing, is underway and will be presented in the future.

Weave Architectures

The multilayer woven fabrics evaluated in this work consisted of alternate layers of warp and weft tows linked with weft binders. The three binder architectures shown in Fig. 1 have been investigated at the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Limited due to their potential for good in-plane properties, since warp and weft tows were nominally straight, and improved impact tolerance, due to the presence of through thickness binders.

The idealised orthogonal architecture shown in Fig. 1 (a) contained reinforcing binders perpendicular to, and spanning the entire thickness of, the preform. It was found that, rather than remaining perpendicular to the preform, the binders tended towards a sine wave profile because they were pulled as part of the weaving process [5]. This separated the outer layers of warp tows and produced large resin rich channels. It was suspected that these channels would act as flaws, providing sites for easy crack initiation, especially under impact loading.

Alternative architectures were therefore designed to reduce the volume of the individual resin rich zones. The normal layered interlock structure, shown in Fig. 1 (b), contained three sets of binders. By reducing the distance that each binder spanned in the through thickness direction then, for the same binder tension as an orthogonal preform, the volume of the resin rich zone was reduced. However the binder configuration in the normal layered interlock structure produced a crimping effect on the warp tows which was expected to reduce the in plane properties [6]. The offset layered interlock structure, in which the central binder was offset by half a unit cell as shown in Fig. 1 (c), was introduced to reduce warp tow crimping through a more uniform distribution of binders.

Fig. 1: Idealised binder distributions in multilayer woven structures. (a) Orthogonal interlock, (b) normal layered interlock, and (c) offset layered interlock

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Preform and Specimen Production

The processing and postcure conditions for these panels have been described elsewhere [7] and are summarised in Table 1. One orthogonal preform and two preforms containing both normal layered interlock and offset layered interlock architectures were woven from E-glass with a mechanical hand loom. Each preform contained six layers of 1440 tex warp tows, five layers of 1200 tex weft tows, and 68 tex weft binders. The preforms were consolidated with Derakane vinyl ester resin using resin transfer moulding. Straight sided, 200 mm x 40 mm with 120 mm gauge length, specimens were cut from the panels in the warp and weft directions. Specimen lengths were limited by material availability, and width was that recommended in ref. [8] to ensure that an adequate number of complete unit cells would be tested and the results representative of the composite.

Table 1: Specimen manufacture details

Panel number	Architecture	Resin	Postcure	No. of specimens	
				Warp	Weft
1	Orthogonal	411-C-50	100 °C/3 h	5	5
2	Normal layered Offset layered	411-45	Room temperature	10	2
				6	2
3	Normal layered Offset layered	411-C-50	100 °C/3 h	2	5
				2	5

Tensile Testing

Tests were conducted in a 100 kN MTS servo hydraulic testing machine using the configuration shown in Fig. 2. A light source was positioned to the rear of the specimen and a 35 mm camera mounted in front. Photographs were taken, with the specimen illuminated by transmitted light, at load increments of approximately 2 kN.

An open weave abrasive cloth (Screenbak) was placed between the specimens and serrated grip faces to soften the gripping interface. This permitted specimens to be tested without tabs but with failure still occurring inside the gauge length.

Specimens were loaded at 0.5 mm min⁻¹ until failure while strain was measured using an MTS 632-12C extensometer modified to a 100 mm gauge length. The increased extensometer gauge length ensured that the effects of damage, which occurred uniformly over the entire specimen gauge length, were measured up to specimen failure. After testing the failed specimens were sectioned, polished and a microstructural examination performed.

Fig. 2: Test configuration showing the specimen, light source, camera, and extended gauge length extensometer

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties

The elastic moduli, evaluated between 1000 and 3000 $\mu\epsilon$, tensile strength and strain to failure are plotted in Fig. 3. The most important parameter controlling mechanical properties was found to be the volume fraction of fibres in the test direction. This was different for each of the specimens due to local variations in architecture, panel thickness and size of the unit cells in the woven preform. Data was therefore normalised to the nominal fibre content for each panel/architecture combination and is shown as the light columns in Fig. 3. The average nominal fibre contents for all architectures was calculated to be 33.3 vol. % in the warp direction and 30.4 vol. % in the weft direction. The contribution of binders to the weft fibre content was ignored. Strength and modulus data were further normalised to these fibre contents and are shown as the dark columns in Fig. 3.

The properties of all architectures in the warp direction and the strain to failure in the weft direction was within the experimental scatter. It was considered valid to compare tests in the warp direction, from Panels 2 and 3, with those in the weft direction, Panel 3 only, since the differences in warp direction modulus and strength between Panels 2 and 3 were typically less than 10 %. The strain to failure of the offset layered interlock, in the warp direction, was 20 % lower in Panel 2, however this was not considered sufficient to invalidate comparisons since this data was still within the overall scatter for all tests.

In the weft direction the data for each panel, light columns, suggested a reduction in modulus and strength as architecture changed from orthogonal to normal layered interlock to offset layered interlock. These differences were reduced to within experimental scatter once the data had been normalised to the standard weft fibre contents, dark columns.

Damage Progression

The form of the stress-strain plot and the features observed in transmitted light photographs were similar for all architectures tested in both directions. These features and behaviours are

Fig. 3: Effect of architecture on; modulus, tensile strength and strain to failure. Light columns show data for each panel and dark columns show data standardised for the fibre content in the test direction. Error bars indicate the range of data

summarised in Fig. 4 and Table 2. Inspection of Table 2 reveals that in some cases the features either occurred in a different order to that shown in Fig. 4, or were not observed at all.

Elastic Range

The unloaded appearance of all specimens was similar to that shown in Fig. 5 (a), with wide warp tow columns separated by thinner resin rich channels. On some specimens the surface legs of the binders were observed, Fig. 5 (e), permitting easy identification of the unit cells.

Preliminary analysis indicates that, in agreement with ref. [1], the elastic modulus of these multilayer woven architectures can be predicted with reasonable accuracy using orthotropic laminate theory. The results of this investigation will be reported during the conference.

Fig. 4: Generalised stress-strain response showing all mechanical behaviour and damage features observed for these architectures and test directions

Table 2: Average strain at which stiffness changes and damage features were observed

Damage or property feature	Orthogonal		Normal layered		Offset layered	
	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft
Primary softening ($\mu\epsilon$)	3340	3530	3090	2540	2990	3130
Modulus drop (%)	26	25	29	19	*	22
Appearance of transverse cracks ($\mu\epsilon$)	6810	5250	3800	5940	4870	4110
Appearance of longitudinal cracks ($\mu\epsilon$)	None	None	8220	14900	6860	15050
Appearance of local disbonding ($\mu\epsilon$)	None	None	13200	None	6850	None
Secondary softening ($\mu\epsilon$)	10610	12280	16730	10670	*	11080
Modulus drop (%)	8	5	13	5	*	14

* Data unavailable

Primary Softening

A 20 to 30 % reduction in stiffness was observed for all specimens at approximately 3000 $\mu\epsilon$. It is most likely that this drop was due to transverse cracking, ie. cracks within the tows oriented perpendicular to the test direction. These cracks were observed in transmitted light photographs and are discussed in the next section. Although the transverse cracks were

observed well after softening had occurred it is probable that the cracks were present earlier but not detected. Interrupted testing will be performed to confirm that this was the case.

Transverse Cracking

Transverse cracks, as shown in Fig. 5 (b), initiated between 3040 and 7160 $\mu\epsilon$ and occurred in all specimens. Cross-sections, such as Fig. 5 (c), show that these cracks were confined exclusively to the tows transverse to the testing direction and did not extend into the surrounding resin rich zones. The number and length of individual cracks increased with load until, at approximately 50 % of failure load, saturation occurred. At this stage cracks spanned most of the specimen width and were uniformly spaced along the full gauge length, similar to the transverse cracks that appear in cross ply laminates.

Load was transferred from tows parallel to the test direction to tows perpendicular to the test direction by shearing of the matrix at the interface between parallel/perpendicular tows. The efficiency of this transfer was probably enhanced by the presence of through thickness binders. Cracking occurred when stress in the perpendicular tows exceeded the matrix tensile strength. It is proposed that this cracking reduced the contribution of perpendicular tows to the load bearing capacity of the composite and so caused the primary softening. Models relating the spacing of transverse cracks and the degree of softening in cross-ply laminates [9] probably apply to the multilayer woven composites used in this work.

When testing in the warp direction the cracks in the weft tows were very clear, appearing straight in orthogonal and normal layered interlock specimens but wavy in offset layered interlock specimens. Most property models account for out of plane tow deviations, however Fig. 5 (e) shows that if the weaving or RTM processes have not been optimised, then in plane deviations, of similar magnitude to out of plane deviations could occur. Figure 3 shows that the effect of weft tow waviness on the specimens tested in this work was not significant.

Secondary Softening

In most specimens a second change in stiffness was observed at higher strains. The response of the specimens that did not display this behaviour; two orthogonal warp, one orthogonal weft and two normal layered interlock warp, were either bilinear or continuously curved.

The resin for the secondary softening is unknown. It is possible that, in normal layered interlock specimens tested in the warp direction, this softening was caused by easier straightening of load bearing tows afforded by the presence of longitudinal cracking and local disbonding. In all other cases the transmitted light photographs either did not detect cracks, or cracks were observed after softening. Again interrupted testing will be performed to determine the precise order of events.

Tow lock-up in the woven architecture has been proposed as a mechanism to explain softening at high loads and very large strain to failure for woven carbon/epoxy composites [1]. However in this work the secondary softening occurred as low as 9000 $\mu\epsilon$ and 250 MPa. It is very unlikely that tow failure would commence at such low strains.

Fig. 5: Transmitted light photographs and cross-sectional micrographs of various specimens indicating the progression of damage. (a) A specimen prior to testing. (b) Transverse cracks. (c) Micrograph showing transverse cracks occurred wholly within perpendicular tows. (d) Longitudinal cracks. (e) Local disbonds. (f) Micrograph showing disbonds as circumferential cracks around the outer tows

Longitudinal Cracking

Longitudinal cracks, as shown in Fig. 5 (d), appeared at intermediate loads within tows parallel to the loading direction. Cracks appeared to initiate under the binder/warp tow crossover point then propagate within the tow to almost the full specimen gauge length.

The most likely cause of these cracks originated during weaving of the preform. Tension in the binders crimped the warp tows at the warp tow/binder crossover point. In the consolidated composite under load, these crimped warp tows tended to straighten and return to their original cross-sectional shape. This produced a tensile stress perpendicular to the tow and cracking if the resin strength was exceeded. This mechanism assumes that, although binders exert considerable restraint on warp tows, they cannot completely prevent all lateral movement.

Local Disbonding

Local disbonding was observed when testing the offset layered interlock specimens, and to a lesser extent the normal layered interlock specimens, in the warp direction. As shown in Fig. 5 (e) disbonding occurred in the region immediately surrounding the warp tow/binder crossover point and was initiated where a short longitudinal crack had reached the surface of a warp tow. Figure 5 (f) showed that these disbonds were restricted to the surface tows, where crimping in the warp tow by the weft binder was most severe.

Disbonding occurred in the most severely crimped regions of tows when the stress at the warp tow/matrix interface, generated by tow straightening, exceeded the tow/matrix interfacial shear strength. Disbonding was confined to the crimped region and crack size depended on the severity of the crimp. Disbonds were much larger in the offset layered interlock specimens, supporting the observations that the tows in this structure were more wavy than those in the other architectures. This increased tow waviness was caused by high binder tension during weaving and is discussed below.

Additional Comments

The extent of crimping in tows parallel to the loading direction controlled the appearance of longitudinal cracks and local disbonds. This crimp was generated not only by the weave architecture, but also by the weaving process, in particular the binder tension. The preforms in this work were woven on a manual loom, with control over binder tension provided by the operator. Due to the difficulties in exerting close control over binder tension it is likely that the degree of crimp in any one preform, let alone between preforms, was variable. In fact the ideal architectures were probably never achieved, however test results indicate that provided this variation was less than 5 to 10° the effect on tensile properties was minimal.

The resin rich channels did not appear to contribute to crack formation. Strains within these channels were very close to the overall specimen strain, and specimen failure strains of 1.6 to 2.4 % were well within the resin capacity of 5 to 6 % [10]. The strain within tows, magnified due to the close packing of glass fibres, was sufficient to cause extensive local cracking [11].

Architectural differences are expected to play a much more significant role when the composites are subjected to compression and impact loading. In these situations two

competing factors will influence performance. The first is the volume of the resin rich zones, increasing of which will reduce performance, and the straightness of tows, where more crimped tows will decrease performance. The volume of resin rich zones decreased from orthogonal to normal layered interlock to offset layered interlock, while tow straightness was controlled by architecture and weaving technique. The effect of each factor must be determined experimentally.

CONCLUSIONS

There was no significant difference in the elastic modulus, strength and strain to failure of glass/vinyl ester orthogonal, normal layered interlock and offset layered interlock architectures when tested in the warp and weft directions, provided the effect of fibre content in the testing direction was accounted for.

Five features were identified during the tensile loading of these materials; (i) primary softening, (ii) cracks within tows transverse to the testing direction, (iii) secondary softening, (iv) cracks within tows parallel to the testing direction, (v) local disbonding at the warp tow/binder crossover. The softening events were probably caused by cracking and disbonding.

Transmitted light photography is a useful technique for characterising damage accumulation in translucent composite specimens during testing. It has contributed to an understanding of failure mechanisms and assisted in more detailed examination of these materials.

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